

Multiple attribute decision-making method under hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic environment

Jun Ye*

Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Shaoxing University, 508 Huancheng West
Road, Shaoxing, Zhejiang Province 312000, P.R. China

Abstract: Motivated by the ideas of interval neutrosophic linguistic sets (INLSs) and hesitant fuzzy sets (HFSs), this paper proposes the concept of hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic sets (HINLSs) and defines the operational laws of hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic elements (HINLEs) and the score, accuracy and certainty functions for HINLEs. Then, a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted average (HINLWA) operator and a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted geometric (HINLWG) operator are developed to aggregate the hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic information. Moreover, some desirable properties of the two operators are investigated. A decision-making method based on the HINLWA and HINLWG operators is developed to handle multiple attribute decision making problems, in which attribute values with respect to alternatives take the form of HINLEs, under a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic environment. Finally, an illustrative example about investment alternatives is given to demonstrate the application of the developed method.

Keywords: Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic set; Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic

* Tel.: +86-575-88327323

E-mail address: yehjun@aliyun.com (Jun Ye)

1 element; Score function; Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted average (HINLWA)
2
3 operator; Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted geometric (HINLWG) operator;
4
5
6 Decision making
7
8
9
10
11
12
13

14 1. Introduction

15
16 The neutrosophic set proposed firstly by Smarandache [1] generalizes an intuitionistic fuzzy set
17 and an interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set from philosophical point of view and its functions
18
19 $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$, i.e., $T_A(x): X \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$,
20
21 $I_A(x): X \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$, and $F_A(x): X \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$. The neutrosophic set can be better to express incomplete,
22
23 indeterminate and inconsistent information. However, the nonstandard interval $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ is difficult to
24
25 apply in real scientific and engineering areas. Hence, some researchers have introduced some
26
27 subclasses of the neutrosophic set to easily apply in real scientific and engineering areas by
28
29 constraining the nonstandard interval $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ into the real standard interval $[0, 1]$ for its functions
30
31 $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$. Firstly, Wang et al. [2, 3] introduced the concepts of an interval neutrosophic
32
33 set (INS) and a single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS), which are the subclasses of a neutrosophic
34
35 set, and provided the set-theoretic operators and various properties of SVNSs and INSs. Then, Ye [4]
36
37 proposed a correlation coefficient of SVNSs and applied it to multiple attribute decision-making
38
39 problems with single-valued neutrosophic information. Ye [5] presented a single-valued
40
41 neutrosophic cross-entropy measure for single-valued neutrosophic multiple attribute
42
43 decision-making problems. Liu and Wang [6] presented single-valued neutrosophic normalized
44
45 weighted Bonferroni mean operators and applied them to decision making problems with
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 single-valued neutrosophic information. Further, Liu et al. [7] developed some generalized
2
3 single-valued neutrosophic number Hamacher aggregation operators and their application to group
4
5 decision making problems with single-valued neutrosophic information. On the other hand, Chi and
6
7 Liu [8] extended a TOPSIS method to interval neutrosophic multiple attribute decision-making
8
9 problems. Ye [9] introduced the distances-based similarity measures of INSs and their applications in
10
11 multiple attribute decision-making under interval neutrosophic environment. Zhang et al. [10] put
12
13 forward the score, accuracy, and certainty functions of an interval neutrosophic number (INN) and
14
15 introduced the interval neutrosophic number weighted average (INNWA) operator and interval
16
17 neutrosophic number weighted geometric (INNWG) operator for interval neutrosophic multiple
18
19 attribute decision-making problems.
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27

28 Currently, based on the combination of interval neutrosophic sets and linguistic variables [11],
29
30 Ye [12] defined the concept of interval neutrosophic linguistic sets (INLSs) and the score, accuracy
31
32 and certainty functions of an interval neutrosophic linguistic number (INLN), and then developed an
33
34 interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted average (INLWA) operator and an interval neutrosophic
35
36 linguistic weighted geometric (INLWG) operator to handle multiple attribute decision-making
37
38 problems with interval neutrosophic linguistic information. Since a single-valued neutrosophic
39
40 linguistic set is a special case of an interval neutrosophic linguistic set, Ye [13] proposed an extended
41
42 TOPSIS method for multiple attribute group decision-making problems with single-valued
43
44 neutrosophic linguistic numbers. Furthermore, by the combination of SVNNS and hesitant fuzzy sets
45
46 (HFSs) [14, 15], Ye [16] presented a single-valued neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy set (SVNHFS), a
47
48 single-valued neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy weighted average (SVNHFWA) operator and a
49
50 single-valued neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy weighted geometric (SVNHFWG) operator, then applied
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 them to multiple attribute decision-making problems under a single-valued neutrosophic hesitant
2
3 fuzzy environment. Then, Liu and Shi [17] further developed the generalized hybrid weighted
4
5 average operator of interval neutrosophic hesitant set and its multiple attribute decision making
6
7 method.
8
9

10
11 An INLN introduced in [12] contains the linguistic variable represented by decision maker's
12
13 judgment to an evaluated object and the subjective evaluation value represented by an INN as the
14
15 reliability of the given linguistic variable. However, in complex decision making problems, when
16
17 decision makers give their assessments on attributes by the form of INLNs, they may also be hesitant
18
19 among several possible INLNs. For example, for a predefined linguistic term set $S = \{s_0, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4,$
20
21 $s_5, s_6\} = \{\text{extremely low, very low, low, medium, high, very high, extremely high}\}$, evaluating the
22
23 "growth" of a company, we can utilize a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic element (HINLE)
24
25 $\{\langle s_2, ([0.7,0.8], [0.0,0.1], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_3, ([0.6,0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.5,0.6], [0.2, 0.3],$
26
27 $[0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$ as its evaluation, where s_2, s_3 and s_4 indicate that the "growth" of a company may be
28
29 "low", "medium" and "high", and the INNs "([0.7,0.8], [0.0,0.1], [0.1, 0.2])", "([0.6,0.7], [0.1, 0.2],
30
31 [0.1, 0.2])" and "([0.5,0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.2, 0.3])" indicate that the "growth" of a company may
32
33 contain truth degrees, indeterminacy degrees and falsity degrees belonging to s_2, s_3 and $s_4,$
34
35 respectively. In this case, the existing methods are not suitable for dealing with the decision making
36
37 problems with hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic information. Motivated by the concepts of
38
39 INLSs and HFSs, the purposes of this paper are: (1) to propose the concepts of a hesitant interval
40
41 neutrosophic linguistic set (HINLS) and the HINLE which is composed of a set of INLNs, (2) to
42
43 define the operational laws of HINLEs and the score, accuracy and certainty functions for HINLEs,
44
45 (3) to propose a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted average (HINLWA) operator and a
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted geometric (HINLWG) operator and to investigate their properties, and (4) to establish a decision-making method based on the HINLWA and HINLWG operators to handle multiple attribute decision-making problems with hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic information. To do so, the rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly describes some concepts of INLSs and HFSs. In Section 3, we propose the concepts of HINLSs and HINLEs and define the operational laws of HINLEs and the score, accuracy and certainty functions for HINLEs. Section 4 develops the HINLWA and HINLWG operators and investigates their some properties. Section 5 establishes a multiple attribute decision-making approach based on the HINLWA and HINLWG operators and the score, accuracy and certainty functions. An illustrative example about investment alternatives is provided in Section 6. Section 7 gives conclusions and future research.

2. Preliminaries of INLSs and HFSs

In this section, some basic concepts related to INLSs and HFSs are briefly introduced to utilize the following analysis.

Let $S = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_l\}$ be a finite ordered discrete linguistic term set with old cardinality, where s_i represents a possible value for a linguistic variable and $l+1$ is the cardinality of S . For example, when $l = 6$, we can give a linguistic term set $S = \{s_0, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6\} = \{\text{extremely low, very low, low, medium, high, very high, extremely high}\}$.

In a linguistic term set S , any two linguistic variables s_i and s_j must satisfy the following properties [18, 19]:

- (1) The set is ordered: $s_i \geq s_j$ if $i \geq j$,

1 (2) Negation operator is $\text{neg}(s_i) = s_{1-i}$,

2
3 (3) Maximum operator is $\max(s_i, s_j) = s_i$ if $i > j$,

4
5
6 (4) Minimum operator is $\min(s_i, s_j) = s_j$ if $i > j$.

7
8
9 **2.1. Interval neutrosophic linguistic sets**

10
11 Ye [12] presented the concept of an INLS and gave its definition.

12
13
14 **Definition 1** [12]. Let X be a finite universal set. An INLS in X is defined by

$$15 \quad A = \left\{ \left\langle x, [s_{\theta(x)}, (T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x))] \right\rangle \mid x \in X \right\},$$

16
17 where $s_{\theta(x)} \in S$, $T_A(x) = [\inf T_A(x), \sup T_A(x)] \subseteq [0, 1]$, $I_A(x) = [\inf I_A(x), \sup I_A(x)] \subseteq [0, 1]$ and $F_A(x) =$
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
[$\inf F_A(x), \sup F_A(x)$] $\subseteq [0, 1]$ represent the truth-membership degree, the indeterminacy-membership degree and the falsity-membership degree of the element x in X to the linguistic variable $s_{\theta(x)}$, respectively, with the condition $0 \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3$ for any $x \in X$.

Then, the seven tuple $\langle s_{\theta(x)}, ([\inf T_A(x), \sup T_A(x)], [\inf I_A(x), \sup I_A(x)], [\inf F_A(x), \sup F_A(x)]) \rangle$
in A is called an INLN. For convenience, an INLN can be represented as $a = \langle s_{\theta(a)}, ([T^L(a), T^U(a)], [I^L(a), I^U(a)], [F^L(a), F^U(a)]) \rangle$.

Definition 2 [12]. Let $a_1 = \langle s_{\theta(a_1)}, ([T^L(a_1), T^U(a_1)], [I^L(a_1), I^U(a_1)], [F^L(a_1), F^U(a_1)]) \rangle$ and $a_2 = \langle s_{\theta(a_2)}, ([T^L(a_2), T^U(a_2)], [I^L(a_2), I^U(a_2)], [F^L(a_2), F^U(a_2)]) \rangle$ be two INLNs and $\lambda \geq 0$, then the operational laws of INLNs are defined as follows:

$$(1) \quad a_1 + a_2 = \left\langle s_{\theta(a_1) + \theta(a_2)}, \begin{pmatrix} [T^L(a_1) + T^L(a_2) - T^L(a_1)T^L(a_2), \\ T^U(a_1) + T^U(a_2) - T^U(a_1)T^U(a_2)], \\ [I^L(a_1)I^L(a_2), I^U(a_1)I^U(a_2)], \\ [F^L(a_1)F^L(a_2), F^U(a_1)F^U(a_2)] \end{pmatrix} \right\rangle,$$

$$(2) a_1 \times a_2 = \left\langle s_{\theta(a_1) \times \theta(a_2)}, \left(\begin{array}{l} [T^L(a_1)T^L(a_2), T^U(a_1)T^U(a_2)], \\ [I^L(a_1) + I^L(a_2) - I^L(a_1)I^L(a_2), \\ I^U(a_1) + I^U(a_2) - I^U(a_1)I^U(a_2)], \\ [F^L(a_1) + F^L(a_2) - F^L(a_1)F^L(a_2), \\ F^U(a_1) + F^U(a_2) - F^U(a_1)F^U(a_2)] \end{array} \right) \right\rangle,$$

$$(3) \lambda a_1 = \left\langle s_{\lambda \theta(a_1)}, \left(\begin{array}{l} [1 - (1 - T^L(a_1))^\lambda, 1 - (1 - T^U(a_1))^\lambda], \\ [(I^L(a_1))^\lambda, (I^U(a_1))^\lambda], [(F^L(a_1))^\lambda, (F^U(a_1))^\lambda] \end{array} \right) \right\rangle,$$

$$(4) a_1^\lambda = \left\langle s_{\theta^\lambda(a_1)}, \left(\begin{array}{l} [(T^L(a_1))^\lambda, (T^U(a_1))^\lambda], [1 - (1 - I^L(a_1))^\lambda, 1 - (1 - I^U(a_1))^\lambda], \\ [1 - (1 - F^L(a_1))^\lambda, 1 - (1 - F^U(a_1))^\lambda] \end{array} \right) \right\rangle.$$

To rank INLNs, Ye [12] defined the score, accuracy and certainty functions of an INLN.

Definition 3 [12]. Let $a = \langle s_{\alpha(a)}, ([T^L(a), T^U(a)], [I^L(a), I^U(a)], [F^L(a), F^U(a)]) \rangle$ be an INLN. Then,

the score, accuracy and certainty functions for the INLN a are defined, respectively, as follows:

$$E(a) = \frac{(4 + T^L(a) - I^L(a) - F^L(a) + T^U(a) - I^U(a) - F^U(a))\theta(a)}{6l}, \quad (1)$$

$$H(a) = \frac{(T^L(a) - F^L(a) + T^U(a) - F^U(a))\theta(a)}{2l}, \quad (2)$$

$$C(a) = \frac{(T^L(a) + T^U(a))\theta(a)}{2l}. \quad (3)$$

Definition 4 [12]. Let a_1 and a_2 be two INLNs. Then, the ranking method can be defined as follows:

- (1) If $E(a_1) > E(a_2)$, then $a_1 \succ a_2$;
- (2) If $E(a_1) = E(a_2)$ and $H(a_1) > H(a_2)$, then $a_1 \succ a_2$;
- (3) If $E(a_1) = E(a_2)$, $H(a_1) = H(a_2)$, and $C(a_1) > C(a_2)$, then $a_1 \succ a_2$;
- (4) If $E(a_1) = E(a_2)$, $H(a_1) = H(a_2)$, and $C(a_1) = C(a_2)$, then $a_1 = a_2$.

2. 2. Hesitant fuzzy sets

Torra and Narukawa [14] and Torra [15] firstly proposed the concept of a HFS, which is defined

as follows.

Definition 5 [14, 15]. Let X be a fixed set, a hesitant fuzzy set A on X is defined in terms of a function $h_A(x)$ that when applied to X returns a finite subset of $[0, 1]$, which can be represented as the following mathematical symbol:

$$A = \{ \langle x, h_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where $h_A(x) = \bigcup_{\gamma_A(x) \in h_A(x)} \{ \gamma_A(x) \}$ is a set of some different values in $[0, 1]$, denoting the possible membership degrees of the element $x \in X$ to A . For convenience, we call $h_A(x)$ a hesitant fuzzy element [20] denoted simply by h , which reads $h = \bigcup_{\gamma \in h} \{ \gamma \}$ for $\gamma \in [0, 1]$.

According to the relationship between a hesitant fuzzy element and an intuitionistic fuzzy value, Xia and Xu [20] defined some operations on three hesitant fuzzy elements h, h_1, h_2 and a scale $\lambda \geq 0$:

- (1) $h^\lambda = \bigcup_{\gamma \in h} \{ \gamma^\lambda \},$
- (2) $\lambda h = \bigcup_{\gamma \in h} \{ 1 - (1 - \gamma)^\lambda \},$
- (3) $h_1 \oplus h_2 = \bigcup_{\gamma_1 \in h_1, \gamma_2 \in h_2} \{ \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_1 \gamma_2 \},$
- (4) $h_1 \otimes h_2 = \bigcup_{\gamma_1 \in h_1, \gamma_2 \in h_2} \{ \gamma_1 \gamma_2 \}.$

Definition 6 [20]. For a hesitant element h , $G(h) = \frac{1}{\#h} \sum_{\gamma \in h} \gamma$ is called the score function of h , where $\#h$ is the number of the elements in h . For two hesitant elements h_1 and h_2 , if $G(h_1) > G(h_2)$, then $h_1 > h_2$; if $G(h_1) = G(h_2)$, then $h_1 = h_2$.

3. Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic set

Based on the combination of an INLS and a HFS, this section proposes the concepts of a HINLS, a HINLE, which is a basic element in a HINLS, and the operational laws of HINLEs, as well as the appropriate score, accuracy and certainty functions to be suitable for a HINLE.

Definition 7. Let X be a nonempty set of the universe and $S = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_l\}$ be a finite ordered discrete linguistic set. Then, a HINLS in X can be expressed as the following mathematical symbol:

$$N = \{ \langle x, \tilde{n}_N(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where $\tilde{n}_N(x) = \bigcup_{a_N(x) \in \tilde{n}_N(x)} \{a_N(x)\}$ is a set of INLNs, denoting the possible INLNs of the element $x \in X$ to the set N , and $a_N(x) = \langle s_{\alpha(x)}, ([\inf T_N(x), \sup T_N(x)], [\inf I_N(x), \sup I_N(x)], [\inf F_N(x), \sup F_N(x)]) \rangle$ is an INLN. For convenience, $\tilde{n}_N(x) = \bigcup_{a_N(x) \in \tilde{n}_N(x)} \{a_N(x)\}$ in N is simply denoted by $\tilde{n} = \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \{a\}$, where $\tilde{n}$ is called a HINLE and $a = \langle s_{\alpha(a)}, ([T^L(a), T^U(a)], [I^L(a), I^U(a)], [F^L(a), F^U(a)]) \rangle$ is called an INLN. Then, N is the set of all HINLEs.

Definition 8. Let $\tilde{n}, \tilde{n}_1$ and $\tilde{n}_2$ be any three HINLEs and $\lambda \geq 0$, then the operational laws of HINLEs are defined as follows:

$$(1) \tilde{n}_1 + \tilde{n}_2 = \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2} \left\langle S_{\theta(a_1) + \theta(a_2)}, \left[\begin{array}{l} [T^L(a_1) + T^L(a_2) - T^L(a_1)T^L(a_2), \\ T^U(a_1) + T^U(a_2) - T^U(a_1)T^U(a_2)], \\ [I^L(a_1)I^L(a_2), I^U(a_1)I^U(a_2)], \\ [F^L(a_1)F^L(a_2), F^U(a_1)F^U(a_2)] \end{array} \right] \right\rangle,$$

$$(2) \tilde{n}_1 \times \tilde{n}_2 = \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2} \left\langle S_{\theta(a_1) \times \theta(a_2)}, \left[\begin{array}{l} [T^L(a_1)T^L(a_2), T^U(a_1)T^U(a_2)], \\ [I^L(a_1) + I^L(a_2) - I^L(a_1)I^L(a_2), \\ I^U(a_1) + I^U(a_2) - I^U(a_1)I^U(a_2)], \\ [F^L(a_1) + F^L(a_2) - F^L(a_1)F^L(a_2), \\ F^U(a_1) + F^U(a_2) - F^U(a_1)F^U(a_2)] \end{array} \right] \right\rangle,$$

$$(3) \lambda \tilde{n} = \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \left\langle S_{\lambda \theta(a)}, \left[\begin{array}{l} [1 - (1 - T^L(a))^\lambda, 1 - (1 - T^U(a))^\lambda], \\ [(I^L(a))^\lambda, (I^U(a))^\lambda], [(F^L(a))^\lambda, (F^U(a))^\lambda] \end{array} \right] \right\rangle,$$

$$(4) \tilde{n}^\lambda = \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \left\langle S_{\theta^\lambda(a)}, \left[\begin{array}{l} [(T^L(a))^\lambda, (T^U(a))^\lambda], [1 - (1 - I^L(a))^\lambda, 1 - (1 - I^U(a))^\lambda], \\ [1 - (1 - F^L(a))^\lambda, 1 - (1 - F^U(a))^\lambda] \end{array} \right] \right\rangle.$$

Definition 9. Let $\tilde{n}$ be an HINLE. Then, the score, accuracy and certainty functions of the HINLE $\tilde{n}$ are defined, respectively, as follows:

$$E_H(\tilde{n}) = \frac{1}{\#\tilde{n}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{n}} \frac{(4 + T^L(a) - I^L(a) - F^L(a) + T^U(a) - I^U(a) - F^U(a))\theta(a)}{6l}, \quad (4)$$

$$H_H(\tilde{n}) = \frac{1}{\#\tilde{n}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{n}} \frac{(T^L(a) - F^L(a) + T^U(a) - F^U(a))\theta(a)}{2l}, \quad (5)$$

$$C_H(\tilde{n}) = \frac{1}{\#\tilde{n}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{n}} \frac{(T^L(a) + T^U(a))\theta(a)}{2l}. \quad (6)$$

where $\#\tilde{n}$ is the number of INLNs in $\tilde{n}$ and $l+1$ is the cardinality of the linguistic term set S .

Definition 10. Let $\tilde{n}_1$ and $\tilde{n}_2$ be any two HINLEs. Then, the ranking method can be defined as follows:

- (1) If $E_H(\tilde{n}_1) > E_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, then $\tilde{n}_1 \succ \tilde{n}_2$;
- (2) If $E_H(\tilde{n}_1) = E_H(\tilde{n}_2)$ and $H_H(\tilde{n}_1) > H_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, then $\tilde{n}_1 \succ \tilde{n}_2$;
- (3) If $E_H(\tilde{n}_1) = E_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, $H_H(\tilde{n}_1) = H_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, and $C_H(\tilde{n}_1) > C_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, then $\tilde{n}_1 \succ \tilde{n}_2$;
- (4) If $E_H(\tilde{n}_1) = E_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, $H_H(\tilde{n}_1) = H_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, and $C_H(\tilde{n}_1) = C_H(\tilde{n}_2)$, then $\tilde{n}_1 = \tilde{n}_2$.

4. Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted aggregation operators

Based on the operational laws of HINLEs, we can propose two hesitant interval neutrosophic weighted aggregation operators to aggregate hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic information, which are usually utilized in multiple attribute decision making.

4.1 Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted average operator

Definition 11. Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. The HINLWA operator is defined as

$$HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \tilde{n}_j \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weight vector of $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1.$$

Theorem 1. Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. Then by Eq. (7) and the operational laws of HINLEs, we can obtain the following result:

$$\begin{aligned} HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = & \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2, \dots, a_n \in \tilde{n}_n} \left\{ s_{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left[\left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weight vector of $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1.$$

Proof. The proof of Eq. (8) can be done by means of mathematical induction.

(1) When $n = 2$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} w_1 \tilde{n}_1 = & \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1} \left\{ s_{w_1 \theta(a_1)} \left([1 - (1 - T^L(a_1))^{w_1}, 1 - (1 - T^U(a_1))^{w_1}], \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. [(I^L(a_1))^{w_1}, (I^U(a_1))^{w_1}], [(F^L(a_1))^{w_1}, (F^U(a_1))^{w_1}] \right) \right\} \\ w_2 \tilde{n}_2 = & \bigcup_{a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2} \left\{ s_{w_2 \theta(a_2)} \left([1 - (1 - T^L(a_2))^{w_2}, 1 - (1 - T^U(a_2))^{w_2}], \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. [(I^L(a_2))^{w_2}, (I^U(a_2))^{w_2}], [(F^L(a_2))^{w_2}, (F^U(a_2))^{w_2}] \right) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2) = & w_1 \tilde{n}_1 + w_2 \tilde{n}_2 \\ = & \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2} \left\{ s_{\sum_{j=1}^2 w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left([1 - (1 - T^L(a_1))^{w_1} + 1 - (1 - T^L(a_2))^{w_2} - (1 - (1 - T^L(a_1))^{w_1})(1 - (1 - T^L(a_2))^{w_2}), \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. 1 - (1 - T^U(a_1))^{w_1} + 1 - (1 - T^U(a_2))^{w_2} - (1 - (1 - T^U(a_1))^{w_1})(1 - (1 - T^U(a_2))^{w_2}), \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. [(I^L(a_1))^{w_1} (I^L(a_2))^{w_2}, (I^U(a_1))^{w_1} (I^U(a_2))^{w_2}], [(F^L(a_1))^{w_1} (F^L(a_2))^{w_2}, (F^U(a_1))^{w_1} (F^U(a_2))^{w_2}] \right) \right\} \\ = & \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2} \left\{ s_{\sum_{j=1}^2 w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left([1 - (1 - T^L(a_1))^{w_1} (1 - T^L(a_2))^{w_2}, 1 - (1 - T^U(a_1))^{w_1} (1 - T^U(a_2))^{w_2}], \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left[\prod_{j=1}^2 (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^2 (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^2 (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^2 (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

(9)

(2) When $n = k$, by applying Eq. (8), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_k) = \\
 & \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2, \dots, a_k \in \tilde{n}_k} \left\{ \left\langle s_{\sum_{j=1}^k w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left(\left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^k (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^k (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left[\prod_{j=1}^k (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^k (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^k (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^k (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right\rangle \right\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

(3) When $n = k + 1$, by applying Eqs. (9) and (10), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_{k+1}) = \\
 & \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2, \dots, a_{k+1} \in \tilde{n}_{k+1}} \left\{ \left\langle s_{\sum_{j=1}^{k+1} w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left(\left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^k (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j} + 1 - (1 - T^L(a_{k+1}))^{w_{k+1}} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. - (1 - \prod_{j=1}^k (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j})(1 - (1 - T^L(a_{k+1}))^{w_{k+1}}), \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1 - \prod_{j=1}^k (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j} + 1 - (1 - T^U(a_{k+1}))^{w_{k+1}} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. - (1 - \prod_{j=1}^k (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j})(1 - (1 - T^U(a_{k+1}))^{w_{k+1}}) \right], \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \left[\prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right\rangle \right\} \\
 & = \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2, \dots, a_{k+1} \in \tilde{n}_{k+1}} \left\{ \left\langle s_{\sum_{j=1}^{k+1} w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left(\left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left[\prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^{k+1} (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right\rangle \right\} .
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from the above results, we have Eq. (8) for any n . This completes the proof. $\square$

Especially, if $\mathbf{W} = (1/n, 1/n, \dots, 1/n)^T$, then the *HINLWA* operator reduces to a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic average operator for HINLEs.

It is obvious that some desired properties of the *HINLWA* operator are given as follows:

(1) Idempotency: Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. If $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is

equal and $\tilde{n}_j = \tilde{n} = \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \{s_{\theta(a)}, (T(a), I(a), F(a))\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $T(a), I(a), F(a) \subseteq [0, 1]$, then there is $HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = \tilde{n}$.

(2) Boundedness: Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. If

$$s_{\theta^-} = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{s_{\theta(a_j)} | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad s_{\theta^+} = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{s_{\theta(a_j)} | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad T^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{T(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\},$$

$$T^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{T(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad I^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{I(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad I^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{I(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\},$$

$$F^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{F(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad F^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{F(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\} \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, n, \text{ then there is}$$

$$\langle s_{\theta^-}, (T^-, I^+, F^+) \rangle \leq HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) \leq \langle s_{\theta^+}, (T^+, I^-, F^-) \rangle.$$

Proof.

(1) If $\tilde{n}_j = \tilde{n} = \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \{s_{\theta(a)}, (T(a), I(a), F(a))\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $T(a), I(a), F(a) \subseteq [0, 1]$,

we have

$$HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2, \dots, a_n \in \tilde{n}_n} \left\{ \left\langle s_{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \theta(a_j)}, \left([1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j}], [1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j}], \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right\rangle \right\}$$

$$= \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \left\{ \left\langle s_{\theta(a) \sum_{j=1}^n w_j}, \left([1 - (1 - T^L(a))^{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j}], [1 - (1 - T^U(a))^{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j}], \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left[(I^L(a))^{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j}, (I^U(a))^{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j} \right], \left[(F^L(a))^{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j}, (F^U(a))^{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j} \right] \right\rangle \right\}$$

$$= \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \{s_{\theta(a)}, (T^L(a), T^U(a)), [I^L(a), I^U(a)], [F^L(a), F^U(a)]\}$$

$$= \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \{s_{\theta(a)}, (T(a), I(a), F(a))\} = \tilde{n}$$

(2) Since $s_{\theta^-} = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{s_{\theta(a_j)} | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $s_{\theta^+} = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{s_{\theta(a_j)} | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $T^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{T(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$,

$$T^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{T(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad I^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{I(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}, \quad I^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{I(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\},$$

$F^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{F(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $F^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{F(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, then there are

$$\theta^- \leq \theta(a_j) \leq \theta^+, \quad T^- \leq T(a_j) \leq T^+, \quad I^- \leq I(a_j) \leq I^+, \quad F^- \leq F(a_j) \leq F^+ \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \text{ We}$$

have

$$\theta(a) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \theta(a_j) \geq \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \theta^- = \theta^-,$$

$$T(a) = \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \geq \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^{L-})^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^{U-})^{w_j} \right] = T^-,$$

$$I(a) = \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \leq \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (I^{L+})^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (I^{U+})^{w_j} \right] = I^+,$$

$$F(a) = \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \leq \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (F^{L+})^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (F^{U+})^{w_j} \right] = F^+.$$

Then, there are the following scores:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\#\tilde{n}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{n}} \frac{\theta(a)(4 + T^L(a) + T^U(a) - I^L(a) - I^U(a) - F^L(a) - F^U(a))}{6l} = \\ & \frac{1}{\#\tilde{n}} \sum_{a \in \tilde{n}} \left\{ \frac{1}{6l} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \theta(a_j) \right) \left(\begin{aligned} & 4 + 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^L(a_j))^{w_j} + 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^U(a_j))^{w_j} \\ & - \prod_{j=1}^n (I^L(a_j))^{w_j} - \prod_{j=1}^n (I^U(a_j))^{w_j} - \prod_{j=1}^n (F^L(a_j))^{w_j} - \prod_{j=1}^n (F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \end{aligned} \right) \right\} \\ & \geq \frac{\theta^-(4 + T^{L-} + T^{U-} - I^{L+} - I^{U+} - F^{L+} - F^{U+})}{6l}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\#\tilde{n}$ is the number of INLNs in $\tilde{n} = HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n)$ and $l+1$ is the cardinality of the

linguistic term set S . Therefore, according to Definition 10, there is

$$\langle s_{\theta^-}, (T^-, I^+, F^+) \rangle \leq HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n).$$

Similarly, there is $HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) \leq \langle s_{\theta^+}, (T^+, I^-, F^-) \rangle$.

Thus, there is $\langle s_{\theta^-}, (T^-, I^+, F^+) \rangle \leq HINLWA(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) \leq \langle s_{\theta^+}, (T^+, I^-, F^-) \rangle$.

Hence, we complete the proofs of these properties. $\square$

4.2 Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic weighted geometric operator

Definition 12. Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. Then the HINLWG operator is defined as

$$HINLWG(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{n}_j^{w_j} \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weight vector of $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), $w_j \in [0,1]$ and

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1.$$

Theorem 2. Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. by Eq. (11) and the operational laws

of HINLEs, we have the following result:

$$HINLWG(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = \bigcup_{a_1 \in \tilde{n}_1, a_2 \in \tilde{n}_2, \dots, a_n \in \tilde{n}_n} \left\{ \left\langle s_{\prod_{j=1}^n \theta^{w_j}(a_j)}, \left(\prod_{j=1}^n (T^L(a_j))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (T^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right), \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - I^L(a_j))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - I^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right], \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - F^L(a_j))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - F^U(a_j))^{w_j} \right] \right\rangle \right\}, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weight vector of $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), $w_j \in [0,1]$ and

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1.$$

The proof of Theorem 2 can be also given by the similar proof of Theorem 1 (omitted).

Especially, if $\mathbf{W} = (1/n, 1/n, \dots, 1/n)^T$, then the HINLWG operator reduces to a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic geometric operator.

It is obvious that some desired properties of the HINLWG operator are also given as follows:

(1) Idempotency: Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. If $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is

equal and $\tilde{n}_j = \tilde{n} = \bigcup_{a \in \tilde{n}} \left\langle s_{\theta(a)}, (T(a), I(a), F(a)) \right\rangle$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $T(a), I(a), F(a) \subseteq$

$[0, 1]$, then there is $HINLWG(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) = \tilde{n}$.

(2) Boundedness: Let $\tilde{n}_j$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) be a collection of HINLEs. If

$s_{\theta^-} = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{s_{\theta(a_j)} | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $s_{\theta^+} = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{s_{\theta(a_j)} | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $T^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{T(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$,

$T^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{T(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $I^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{I(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $I^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{I(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$,

$F^- = \min_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{F(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$, $F^+ = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} \{F(a_j) | a_j \in \tilde{n}_j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, then there is

$\langle s_{\theta^-}, (T^-, I^+, F^+) \rangle \leq HINLWG(\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2, \dots, \tilde{n}_n) \leq \langle s_{\theta^+}, (T^+, I^-, F^-) \rangle$.

Since the process to prove these properties is similar to the above proofs, it is not repeated here.

5. Decision-making method based on the HINLWA and HINLWG operators

This section proposes a multiple attribute decision-making method based on the HINLWA and HINLWG operators and the score, accuracy and certainty functions of HINLEs under a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic environment.

For a multiple attribute decision-making problem, let $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m\}$ be a set of alternatives and let $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ be a set of attributes. Assume that the weight of the attribute C_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), entered by the decision-maker, is w_j , $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$. In the decision process, the evaluation information of the alternative A_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) on the attribute C_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is represented by a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic decision matrix denoted by $D = (\tilde{n}_{ij})_{n \times m}$, where $\tilde{n}_{ij}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is a HINLE $\tilde{n}_{ij} = \bigcup_{a_{ij} \in \tilde{n}_{ij}} \{a_{ij}\}$ and $a_{ij} = \langle s_{\theta(a_{ij})}, ([T^L(a_{ij}), T^U(a_{ij})], [I^L(a_{ij}), I^U(a_{ij})], [F^L(a_{ij}), F^U(a_{ij})]) \rangle$ is an INLN.

Then, the HINLWA operator or the HINLWG operator is utilized to establish a multiple attribute decision making method under a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic environment, which includes the following steps:

Step 1: By applying Eq. (8) or Eq. (12), the individual overall HINLE $\tilde{n}_i$ for A_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) is calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{n}_i &= \bigcup_{a_i \in \tilde{n}_i} \{a_i\} = \text{HINLWA}(\tilde{n}_{i1}, \tilde{n}_{i2}, \dots, \tilde{n}_{in}) \\ &= \bigcup_{a_{i1} \in \tilde{n}_{i1}, a_{i2} \in \tilde{n}_{i2}, \dots, a_{in} \in \tilde{n}_{in}} \left\langle \left[\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \theta(a_{ij}) \right], \left[\begin{array}{l} \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^L(a_{ij}))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - T^U(a_{ij}))^{w_j} \right], \\ \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (I^L(a_{ij}))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (I^U(a_{ij}))^{w_j} \right], \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (F^L(a_{ij}))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (F^U(a_{ij}))^{w_j} \right] \end{array} \right] \right\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad \text{c(13)}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{n}_i &= \bigcup_{a_i \in \tilde{n}_i} \{a_i\} = \text{HINLWG}(\tilde{n}_{i1}, \tilde{n}_{i2}, \dots, \tilde{n}_{in}) \\
&= \bigcup_{a_{i1} \in \tilde{n}_{i1}, a_{i2} \in \tilde{n}_{i2}, \dots, a_{in} \in \tilde{n}_{in}} \left\{ s \prod_{j=1}^n \theta^{w_j}(a_{ij}), \left[\begin{array}{l} \left[\prod_{j=1}^n (T^L(a_{ij}))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n (T^U(a_{ij}))^{w_j} \right], \\ \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - I^L(a_{ij}))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - I^U(a_{ij}))^{w_j} \right], \\ \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - F^L(a_{ij}))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - F^U(a_{ij}))^{w_j} \right] \end{array} \right] \right\}. \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Calculate the values of the score function $E_H(\tilde{n}_i)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) (accuracy function $H_H(\tilde{n}_i)$), certainty function $C_H(\tilde{n}_i)$) by using Eq. (4) (Eqs. (5) and (6)).

Step 3: Rank the alternatives according to the values of $E_H(\tilde{n}_i)$ ($H_H(\tilde{n}_i)$ and $C_H(\tilde{n}_i)$) ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) and then the largest score value is the best one.

Step 4: End.

6. Illustrative example

An illustrative example about investment alternatives adapted from Ye [12, 16] is used as the application of the proposed decision-making method under a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic environment. An investment company wants to invest a sum of money in the best option. To invest the money, there is a panel with four possible alternatives: A_1 (a car company), A_2 (a food company), A_3 (a computer company) and A_4 (an arms company). The investment company must take a decision according to the three attributes: C_1 (the risk), C_2 (the growth) and C_3 (the environmental impact). The vector of the attribute weights is given as $\mathbf{W} = (0.35, 0.25, 0.4)^T$. Three decision makers are invited to evaluate the four possible alternatives of A_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) with respect to the three attributes of C_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) by the form of HINLEs under the linguistic term set $S = \{s_1 = \text{extremely poor}, s_2 = \text{very poor}, s_3 = \text{poor}, s_4 = \text{medium}, s_5 = \text{good}, s_6 = \text{very good}, s_7 = \text{extremely good}\}$.

For example, the HINLE of an alternative A_1 with respect to an attribute C_1 is given as $\{\langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle\}$ by the three decision makers, which indicates that the assessment of the alternative A_1 with respect to the attribute C_1 is about the linguistic value s_4 with the satisfaction degree $[0.5, 0.6]$, dissatisfaction degree $[0.2, 0.3]$, and indeterminacy degree $[0.1, 0.2]$ given by two experts of them and about the linguistic value s_5 with the satisfaction degree $[0.3, 0.4]$, dissatisfaction degree $[0.3, 0.4]$ and indeterminacy degree $[0.2, 0.3]$ given by one expert of them. Thus, when the four possible alternatives with respect to the above three attributes are evaluated by the three decision makers, the hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic decision matrix is constructed as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic decision matrix D

	C_1	C_2	C_3
A_1	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_5, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.4, 0.5], [0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.5]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.5, 0.6]) \rangle\}$
A_2	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.7, 0.8], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.6, 0.7], [0, 0.1], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.7, 0.8], [0, 0.1], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$
A_3	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.7, 0.9], [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.5], [0.1, 0.2], [0.4, 0.5]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{ \langle s_3, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], \\
& [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], \quad \{ \langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], \\
& \{ \langle s_3, ([0.7, 0.8], [0, 0.1], [0.1, \\
A_4 & [0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle, \langle s_5, \quad [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.5], \\
& 0.2]) \rangle \} \\
& ([0.4, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, \quad [0, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle \} \\
& 0.2]) \rangle \}
\end{aligned}$$

Then, the developed approach is utilized to obtain the ranking order of the alternatives and the most desirable one(s), which can be described as the following steps:

Step 1: Aggregate all HINLEs of $\tilde{n}_{ij}$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4; j = 1, 2, 3$) by using the HINLWA operator to derive the collective HINLE $\tilde{n}_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) for an alternative A_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$). Taking an alternative A_1 for an example, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{n}_1 &= HINLWA(\tilde{n}_{11}, \tilde{n}_{12}, \tilde{n}_{13}) \\
&= \bigcup_{a_{11} \in \tilde{n}_{11}, a_{12} \in \tilde{n}_{12}, a_{13} \in \tilde{n}_{13}} \left\{ s_{\sum_{j=1}^3 w_j \theta(a_{1j})}, \left(\left[\begin{array}{l} 1 - \prod_{j=1}^3 (1 - T^L(a_{1j}))^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^3 (1 - T^U(a_{1j}))^{w_j} \\ \prod_{j=1}^3 (I^L(a_{1j}))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^3 (I^U(a_{1j}))^{w_j} \\ \prod_{j=1}^3 (F^L(a_{1j}))^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^3 (F^U(a_{1j}))^{w_j} \end{array} \right] \right) \right\} \\
&= \{ \langle s_{3.85}, ([0.4622, 0.5627], [0.1189, 0.2213], [0.2603, 0.3955]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.2}, ([0.395, 0.496], \\
& [0.1516, 0.2551], [0.3000, 0.4373]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.25}, ([0.3966, 0.4996], [0.1189, 0.2213], [0.3193, 0.4254]) \rangle, \\
& \langle s_{4.6}, ([0.3212, 0.4234], [0.1516, 0.2551], [0.3680, 0.4704]) \rangle \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can derive the following collective HINLFEs of $\tilde{n}_i$ ($i = 2, 3, 4$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{n}_2 &= \{ \langle s_{3.6}, ([0.6776, 0.7787], [0, 0.1275], [0.1516, 0.2551]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.6383, 0.7397], [0, \\
& 0.1682], [0.1516, 0.2551]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.4}, ([0.6045, 0.7079], [0, 0.1682], [0.2000, 0.3000]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.95}, ([0.6435, \\
& 0.7449], [0, 0.1275], [0.1189, 0.2551]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.35}, ([0.6000, 0.7000], [0, 0.1682], [0.1189, 0.2551]) \rangle, \\
& \langle s_{4.75}, ([0.5627, 0.6634], [0, 0.1682], [0.1569, 0.3000]) \rangle \};
\end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{n}_3 = \{\langle s_{3.6}, ([0.5819, 0.7538], [0.1516, 0.3318], [0.1737, 0.2797]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.85}, ([0.5452, 0.7396], [0.1275, 0.2998], [0.1866, 0.2958]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.95}, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1747, 0.3318], [0.2213, 0.3224]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.2}, ([0.4561, 0.5771], [0.1469, 0.2998], [0.2378, 0.3409]) \rangle\};$$

$$\tilde{n}_4 = \{\langle s_{3.4}, ([0.6045, 0.7079], [0, 0.1569], [0.1189, 0.2213]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.8}, ([0.5476, 0.6807], [0, 0.1569], [0.1189, 0.2213]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.65}, ([0.5819, 0.6862], [0, 0.1569], [0.1316, 0.2378]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.05}, ([0.5216, 0.6569], [0, 0.1569], [0.1316, 0.2378]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.9}, ([0.5624, 0.6682], [0, 0.1737], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.3}, ([0.4993, 0.6372], [0, 0.1737], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle\}.$$

Step 2: Calculate the score values of the collective HINLFE $\tilde{n}_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) by Eq. (4):

$$E_H(\tilde{n}_1) = 0.4413, E_H(\tilde{n}_2) = 0.5519, E_H(\tilde{n}_3) = 0.4549, \text{ and } E_H(\tilde{n}_4) = 0.5051.$$

Step 3: Rank the alternatives in accordance with the score values: $A_2 \succ A_4 \succ A_3 \succ A_1$. Therefore, the alternative A_2 is the best choice according to the largest score value.

On the other hand, if the HINLWG operator is utilized in the multiple attribute decision-making problem, the decision-making steps can be described as following:

Step 1': Aggregate all HINLEs of $\tilde{n}_{ij}$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4; j = 1, 2, 3$) by using the HINLWG operator to derive the collective HINLEs of $\tilde{n}_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) for the alternative A_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$):

$$\tilde{n}_1 = \{\langle s_{3.7697}, ([0.4573, 0.5578], [0.1261, 0.2263], [0.2665, 0.4113]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.2295}, ([0.3466, 0.4547], [0.1261, 0.2263], [0.3589, 0.4615]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.076}, ([0.3824, 0.484], [0.1614, 0.2616], [0.3, 0.4422]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.5731}, ([0.2898, 0.3946], [0.1614, 0.2616], [0.3881, 0.4898]) \rangle\};$$

$$\tilde{n}_2 = \{\langle s_{3.5652}, ([0.6735, 0.7737], [0.0362, 0.1363], [0.1614, 0.2616]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.6333, 0.7335], [0.076, 0.1761], [0.1614, 0.2616]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.3734}, ([0.5887, 0.6896], [0.076, 0.1761], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.8548}, ([0.6382, 0.7384], [0.0362, 0.1363], [0.1261, 0.2616]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.3249}, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.076, 0.1761], [0.1261, 0.2616]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.7287}, ([0.5578, 0.6581], [0.076, 0.1761], [0.1663, 0.3]) \rangle\};$$

1 $\tilde{n}_3 = \{\langle s_{3.5652}, ([0.5625, 0.6915], [0.1614, 0.3368], [0.1937, 0.2942]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.7697}, ([0.4951, 0.6607],$
2
3 [0.1363, 0.3143], [0.2242, 0.3257]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.8548}, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1997, 0.3368], [0.2263, 0.3265]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.076},
4
5 ([0.4401, 0.5733], [0.1758, 0.3143], [0.2555, 0.3565]) \rangle\};

6
7
8 $\tilde{n}_4 = \{\langle s_{3.3659}, ([0.5887, 0.6896], [0.0662, 0.1663], [0.1261, 0.2263]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.6801}, ([0.4799, 0.6411],$
9
10 [0.026, 0.1663], [0.1261, 0.2263]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.6169}, ([0.5625, 0.6636], [0.0662, 0.1663], [0.1548, 0.2555]) \rangle,
11
12 $\langle s_{3.9545}, ([0.4585, 0.6169], [0.026, 0.1663], [0.1548, 0.2555]) \rangle, \langle s_{3.8244}, ([0.532, 0.634], [0.0933,$
13
14 0.1937], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_{4.1814}, ([0.4337, 0.5894], [0.0543, 0.1937], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle\}.

15
16
17
18
19 **Step 2'**: Calculate the score values of the collective HINLE $\tilde{n}_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) for the alternative A_i

20
21
22 ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) by Eq. (4) as follows:

23
24
25 $E_H(\tilde{n}_1) = 0.4231, E_H(\tilde{n}_2) = 0.5363, E_H(\tilde{n}_3) = 0.4325, \text{ and } E_H(\tilde{n}_4) = 0.4774.$

26
27
28 **Step 3'**: Rank the alternatives in accordance with the score values: $A_2 \succ A_4 \succ A_3 \succ A_1$. Therefore, the
29
30 alternative A_2 is also the best choice according to the largest score value.

31
32
33 Obviously, above two kinds of ranking orders are identical and the same as the ones in Ye [12,
34
35 16]. Although two kinds of ranking orders based on the HINLWA and HINLWG operators are
36
37 identical, there are different focal points [16] between the HINLWA operator and the HINLWG
38
39 operator. The HINLWA operator emphasizes the group's major points, while the HINLWG operator
40
41 emphasizes the individual major points. Then, decision makers may select one of them according to
42
43 their preference or real requirements.
44
45
46
47
48
49

50
51 Compared with the relative decision making methods based on INLSs and SVNHFSs, the
52
53 decision making method in this paper uses HINLS information, while the decision making methods
54
55 in [12, 16] use INLS information and SVNHFS information, respectively. Since HINLS is a further
56
57 generalization of INLS and SVNHFS, HINLS information includes INLS information and SVNHFS
58
59

1 information, and also the INLWA and INLWG operators and the SVNHFWA and SVNHFWG
2
3 operators are special cases of the HINLWA and HINLWG operators. Therefore, the decision-making
4
5 method proposed in this paper can deal with not only hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic
6
7 decision-making problems but also single-valued neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy multiple attribute
8
9 decision-making problems and interval neutrosophic linguistic multiple attribute decision-making
10
11 problems. To some extent, the decision-making method in hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic
12
13 setting is more general and more feasible than existing decision-making methods in single-valued
14
15 neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy setting and interval neutrosophic linguistic setting.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24

25 **7. Conclusion**

26
27 This paper introduced the concept of HINLSs based on the combination of both HFSs and
28
29 INLSs as a further generalization of these fuzzy concepts and defined some operational laws of
30
31 HINLEs and the score, accuracy and certainty functions of HINLEs. Then, we proposed the
32
33 HINLWA and HINLWG operators to aggregate hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic information
34
35 and investigated their some properties. Furthermore, the HINLWA and HINLWG operators were
36
37 applied to multiple attribute decision-making problems under a hesitant interval neutrosophic
38
39 linguistic environment, in which attribute values with respect to alternatives are evaluated by the
40
41 form of HINLEs and the attribute weights are known information. We utilized the score function
42
43 (accuracy and certainty functions) to rank the alternatives and to determine the best one(s). Finally,
44
45 an illustrative example was provided to demonstrate the application of the developed
46
47 decision-making approach. The main advantage of the developed method is that it can describe the
48
49 incomplete, indeterminate and inconsistent information by several INLNs in which linguistic
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 variables indicate whether an attribute is good or bad in qualitative and INNs are adopted to
2
3 demonstrate the satisfaction degrees, dissatisfaction degrees and indeterminacy degrees to a
4
5 linguistic variable in quantitative. Therefore, the proposed multiple attribute decision-making
6
7 method under a hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic environment is more suitable for real
8
9 scientific and engineering applications. In the future, we shall further develop more aggregation
10
11 operators for HINLEs and apply them to these areas such as group decision making, expert system,
12
13 information fusion system, fault diagnoses, and medical diagnoses.
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21

22 **Acknowledgment**

23
24
25 This paper was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 71471172).
26
27
28
29
30

31 **References**

- 32
33 [1] Smarandache F (1998) *Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic probability, set, and logic*, American
34
35 *Research Press, Rehoboth, USA.*
36
37
38
39 [2] Wang H, Smarandache F, Zhang YQ, Sunderraman R (2005) *Interval neutrosophic sets and*
40
41 *logic: Theory and applications in computing*, Hexis, Phoenix, AZ.
42
43
44 [3] Wang H, Smarandache F, Zhang YQ, Sunderraman R (2010) *Single valued neutrosophic sets,*
45
46 *Multispace and Multistructure 4: 410-413.*
47
48
49 [4] Ye J (2013) *Multicriteria decision-making method using the correlation coefficient under*
50
51 *single-valued neutrosophic environment*, *International Journal of General Systems* 42(4):
52
53 386-394.
54
55
56
57 [5] Ye J (2014) *Single valued neutrosophic cross-entropy for multicriteria decision making*
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 problems. Applied Mathematical Modelling 38: 1170–1175.

- 2
3 [6] Liu PD, Wang YM (2014) Multiple attribute decision-making method based on single-valued
4
5
6 neutrosophic normalized weighted Bonferroni mean, Neural Computing & Applications, doi:
7
8
9 10.1007/s00521-014-1688-8.
- 10
11 [7] Liu PD, Chu YC, Li YW, Chen YB (2014) Some generalized neutrosophic number Hamacher
12
13 aggregation operators and their application to group decision making, International Journal of
14
15 Fuzzy Systems 16(2): 242-255.
- 16
17 [8] Chi PP, Liu PD (2013) An extended TOPSIS method for the multiple attribute decision making
18
19 problems based on interval neutrosophic sets, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems 1: 63-70.
- 20
21 [9] Ye J (2014) Similarity measures between interval neutrosophic sets and their applications in
22
23 multicriteria decision-making, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems 26: 165-172.
- 24
25 [10] Zhang HY, Wang JQ, Chen XH (2014) Interval neutrosophic sets and their application in
26
27 multicriteria decision making problems, The Scientific World Journal, 2014, Article ID 645953,
28
29 15 pages.
- 30
31 [11] Zadeh LA (1975) The concept of a linguistic variable and its application to approximate
32
33 reasoning Part I, Information Sciences 8(3): 199-249.
- 34
35 [12] Ye J (2014) Some aggregation operators of interval neutrosophic linguistic numbers for
36
37 multiple attribute decision making, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems 27: 2231-2241.
- 38
39 [13] Ye J (2015) An extended TOPSIS method for multiple attribute group decision making based on
40
41 single valued neutrosophic linguistic numbers, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems 28:
42
43 247-255.
- 44
45 [14] Torra V, Narukawa Y (2009) On hesitant fuzzy sets and decision. In: The 18th IEEE
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 International Conference on Fuzzy Systems, Jeju Island, Korea, pp. 1378–1382.

- 2
3 [15] Torra V (2010) Hesitant fuzzy sets, *International Journal of Intelligent Systems* 25: 529–539
4
5
6 [16] Ye J (2015) Multiple-attribute decision-making method under a single-valued neutrosophic
7
8
9 hesitant fuzzy environment, *Journal of Intelligent Systems* 24(1): 23-36.
10
11 [17] Liu P, Shi L (2015) The generalized hybrid weighted average operator based on interval
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21 [18] Herrera F, Herrera-Viedma E, Verdegay JL (1996) A model of consensus in group decision
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31 [19] Herrera F, Herrera-Viedma E (2000) Linguistic decision analysis: Steps for solving decision
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- International Journal of Approximate Reasoning 52: 395–407.

Table 1. Hesitant interval neutrosophic linguistic decision matrix D

	C_1	C_2	C_3
A_1	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_5, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.4, 0.5], [0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.5]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2], [0.5, 0.6]) \rangle\}$ $\{\langle s_3, ([0.7, 0.8], [0, 0.1], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$
A_2	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.7, 0.8], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.3]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.6, 0.7], [0, 0.1], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$
A_3	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.7, 0.9], [0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.2, 0.3], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.5], [0.1, 0.2], [0.4, 0.5]) \rangle\}$ $\{\langle s_3, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.4, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle\}$
A_4	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.7, 0.8], [0, 0.1], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_3, ([0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.2], [0.2, 0.3]) \rangle, \langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.4]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.4, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle\}$	$\{\langle s_4, ([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle, \langle s_5, ([0.3, 0.5], [0, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2]) \rangle\}$